

Cholecystoduodenal Fistula: A Case Report in a Secondary Care Hospital

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Cholecystoduodenal fistula is a rare complication of cholelithiasis, difficult to diagnose preoperatively due to its nonspecific clinical presentation.

Case Report: We present the case of a 57-year-old woman with a long history of cholelithiasis who underwent laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Intraoperatively, a cholecystoduodenal fistula was identified. Subtotal cholecystectomy and primary closure of the duodenal defect were performed, with a favorable outcome.

Conclusion: Timely diagnosis requires a high index of suspicion. The laparoscopic approach is a safe alternative in secondary care hospitals when surgical experience is available.

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INTRODUCTION

Gallstone disease is one of the most common gastrointestinal disorders worldwide and a major cause of outpatient visits, hospitalizations, and surgical interventions in general surgery departments. Its prevalence varies according to ethnic, metabolic, and environmental factors, affecting up to 10–20% of the adult population in Western countries, with a higher incidence in women, obese patients, and older adults (1–3). Symptomatic cholelithiasis and its complications continue to represent a significant burden on healthcare systems, particularly in secondary care hospitals where many patients are initially seen (1,2).

Chronic inflammation of the gallbladder secondary to cholelithiasis can lead to rare but potentially serious complications, most notably bilioenteric fistulas. Cholecystoduodenal fistula is the most common subtype of cholecystoenteric fistulas and originates from persistent inflammatory processes that promote adherence of the gallbladder to the duodenum, with subsequent erosion of the wall and formation of an abnormal communication (3,8). Although its incidence is low, it is associated with increased surgical morbidity and mortality due to the diagnostic and technical challenges involved in its treatment (4,9).

The clinical presentation is usually nonspecific and may manifest as abdominal pain, nausea, vomiting, jaundice, or signs of complicated chronic cholecystitis, which makes preoperative identification difficult (8,10). In many cases, the diagnosis continues to be made incidentally during the surgical procedure, despite the advancement of diagnostic modalities such as computed tomography, magnetic resonance cholangiopancreatography, and endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography (8). Furthermore, some complications arising from these fistulas, such as gallstone ileus, can present significant diagnostic and therapeutic challenges, especially in hospitals with limited resources (6,7).

Currently, the laparoscopic approach has proven to be a feasible and safe alternative in selected patients, allowing for both cholecystectomy and fistula closure to be performed in a single surgical procedure (4,5). However, the presence of severe inflammation, extensive fibrosis, and anatomical distortion increases the risk of injury to the biliary tract and adjacent organs; therefore, management must be individualized according to the clinical conditions and the surgeon's experience (1,4,5). Recent series and case reports have shown favorable results with minimally invasive management, even in complex scenarios associated with a

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sclerotic gallbladder, dense adhesions, or concomitant gallstone ileus (4–6,9).

Due to the low frequency of this condition and the limited evidence from secondary-level hospitals, it is important to share our institutional experience in the diagnosis and treatment of cholecystoduodenal fistula. The objective of this study is to describe the clinical characteristics, intraoperative findings, and surgical management of a case of cholecystoduodenal fistula treated at a secondary-level hospital, as well as to review the recent literature related to this rare complication of biliary lithiasis.

CASE REPORT JUSTIFICATION

Secondary care hospitals play a key role in the management of surgical complications of cholelithiasis. However, the low frequency of cholecystoduodenal fistulas limits clinical experience, so documenting cases contributes to knowledge and improved decisionmaking.

Primary Objective

To describe the surgical management of a cholecystoduodenal fistula in a secondary care hospital.

Methodology

This is an observational, descriptive, retrospective and cross-sectional study of the case report type.

Case Presentation

A 57-year-old woman with a 10 year history of type 2 diabetes mellitus and a 25 year history of facial paralysis. She had undergone phacoemulsification of the left eye six months prior.

She reported an 8-year history of colicky right upper quadrant pain, associated with nausea and vomiting after ingesting cholecystokinetic foods.

On physical examination, the patient was found to be stable, with mild right upper quadrant pain and no signs of peritoneal irritation.

Initial Laboratory Findings: 01/28/26

Complete blood count: WBC $8.71 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$, neutrophils 55.5%, hemoglobin 13.7 g/dL, hematocrit 43.2%, platelets $401,000/\mu\text{L}$

Coagulation profile: PT 11.1 s, PTT 25.8 s, INR 1.01

Biochemistry: Glucose 351 mg/dL, creatinine 0.77 mg/dL, sodium 136.9mEq/L, potassium 4.72 mEq/L, chloride 100 mEq/L Hepatic profile: Total bilirubin 0.22mg/dL (direct 0.14 mg/dL), AST 39.6U/L, ALT 27.9 U/L, alkaline phosphatase 75.8 U/L

Other: LDH 276 U/L, cholesterol 276 mg/dL

Imaging Studies

Abdominal ultrasound: The intra- and extrahepatic biliary tract is of normal course and caliber.

The gallbladder is moderately distended, pear-shaped, measuring 28 x 56 mm along its major axes, with a wall thickness of 2.8 mm. An ovoid gallstone, measuring 18 x 25 mm, is present in the gallbladder body, projecting posterior acoustic shadow. It is slightly mobile with changes in the patient's position, and there is scant biliary sludge. No

perivesicular fluid is observed, and the sonographic Murphy's sign is negative.

The common bile duct in its supraduodenal portion measures 38 mm, and the portal vein measures 8.9 mm, both with normal course and caliber.

Surgical management via laparoscopic cholecystectomy was chosen.

Intraoperative Findings and Management

Operative Results: Approach: Laparoscopic via Veress technique

Duration: 150 minutes

Surgical Technique: Pneumoperitoneum: Established with CO₂ at 12-15 mmHg and initial 12 mm umbilical port for optical trocar. Diagnostic laparoscopy: Identification of severe adhesive syndrome in the right upper quadrant.

Intraoperative findings: Additional ports: one 12 mm subxiphoid port and two 5 mm ports (right anterior and mid-axillary lines).

The gallbladder is observed completely covered with omentum firmly adhered to the liver. Release of adhesions between the gallbladder and omentum, and between the omentum and liver, is initiated. The fundus and upper part of the gallbladder body are released and traction is applied; Hartmann's pouch is not identified. The duodenum is identified as strongly adhered to the gallbladder body. Dissection of the anterior and posterior peritoneal layers continues without identifying any anatomical structures. The duodenum was dissected from the gallbladder, identifying the fistulous tract. The duodenum was freed with blunt dissection and a cold cut, with spontaneous drainage of bile. An impacted intravesicular stone was extracted. Due to the inability to establish a critical view for safety, a subtotal cholecystectomy was performed. Resection was performed at the level of the gallbladder body. The intrahepatic gallbladder was identified as having a stony, friable wall. Hemostasis was then verified, and primary closure of the duodenal orifice was performed in two layers with 3-0 Monocryl and silk Lemberth sutures. The remaining gallbladder was closed with 2-0 silk. Up to this point, there were no apparent bile leaks. An endobag was inserted, and the gallbladder and stone were extracted. Residual fluid was aspirated. A Jackson-Pratt drain was placed into the foramen of Winslow and the surgical bed. Hemostasis was verified. After a complete suture count, the trocars were removed under direct vision, followed by wound closure. The procedures were completed without incident, and the patient was discharged to recovery.

Drainage: Jackson-Pratt in the foramen of Winslow
Hospitalization

The patient progressed favorably, beginning oral intake on the third day.

The drain was removed on the ninth day. She was discharged on the tenth day without complications.

At the 30-day follow-up, she was asymptomatic, and return to activities.

Figure 1 Gallstone

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 2-3 cholecystoduodenal fistula

DISCUSSION

Cholecystoduodenal fistula is an uncommon complication of chronic biliary lithiasis and represents the most frequent type of cholecystoenteric fistula (3,8). Although the incidence of this condition is low, it remains clinically relevant due to the diagnostic and technical difficulties associated with its surgical management, particularly in secondary-level hospitals where these patients frequently receive initial care (1,2).

The case presented shares characteristics described in recent literature, where most patients have a long history of symptomatic cholelithiasis and recurrent episodes of biliary inflammation (4,8,9). The clinical presentation is usually nonspecific and may include abdominal pain, nausea, vomiting, fever, jaundice, or findings consistent with complicated cholecystitis, which makes establishing a preoperative diagnosis difficult (8,10). In our case, the initial diagnostic suspicion pointed toward complicated biliary lithiasis, while the definitive identification of the fistula occurred during the surgical procedure, a situation frequently reported in various studies and case reports (4,8).

Despite advances in diagnostic methods, preoperative detection of cholecystoduodenal fistulas remains a challenge. Studies have shown that even modalities such as endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography (ERCP) may fail to identify the fistulous communication before surgery (8). Similarly, indirect tomographic findings, such as pneumobilia, sclerotic gallbladder, or loss of the sphincter of passage between the gallbladder and duodenum, can guide the diagnosis, although they are not always evident (10). This aligns with our experience, where the definitive diagnosis depended on intraoperative findings and adequate surgical exploration.

From a surgical perspective, the presence of intense fibrosis, chronic inflammation, and anatomical distortion significantly increases the complexity of the procedure and the risk of injury to the common bile duct or adjacent organs (1,4). Current guidelines on cholelithiasis emphasize the importance of individualizing the surgical strategy in complex scenarios and prioritizing patient safety (1). In this context, the surgeon's experience and ability to recognize anatomical variations or associated complications are fundamental to reducing morbidity and mortality.

Traditionally, these fistulas were treated with open surgery due to the technical complexity and high local inflammation; however, laparoscopic surgery has demonstrated favorable results in selected patients (4,5)(5). In our case, surgical treatment allowed us to resolve the pathology in a single procedure, with a favorable postoperative course and no major complications.

Another relevant aspect is the association between cholecystoenteric fistulas and gallstone ileus, considered one of the most severe complications of advanced gallstone disease. The passage of stones into the gastrointestinal tract

through a fistula can cause intestinal obstruction, primarily in elderly patients and those with associated comorbidities (6,7). Although our patient did not present with clinical signs of gallstone ileus, the timely identification and resolution of the fistula likely reduced the risk of progression to this complication.

In secondary-level hospitals, where advanced diagnostic resources may be limited, clinical judgment and diagnostic suspicion play a fundamental role. The experience gained in this case highlights the importance of considering this entity in patients with a history of chronic cholelithiasis and intraoperative findings of severe inflammation or dense adhesions in the hepatoduodenal region.

Finally, due to the limited available evidence and the small number of published series in general hospitals, it is important to continue documenting these types of cases. Clinical reports allow us to expand our knowledge of the presentation, approach, and surgical outcomes of cholecystoduodenal fistulas, contributing to optimizing their recognition and timely treatment in everyday surgical practice.

CONCLUSION

Cholecystoduodenal fistula is a rare complication of cholelithiasis that presents a diagnostic challenge due to its nonspecific clinical presentation. Its timely identification requires a high index of suspicion, especially in patients with a history of long-standing gallstone disease. In secondary-level hospitals, where advanced diagnostic methods may be limited, clinical assessment and appropriate surgical decision-making are essential. In experienced hands, the laparoscopic approach is a safe and effective alternative, allowing for appropriate resolution with the benefits of minimally invasive surgery.

Conflict of interest: There are no conflicts of interest.

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Ethical considerations: The patient was fully informed about the diagnosis, procedures, and potential risks. Written informed consent was obtained for the surgical and anesthetic procedures as well as for publication of this case report.

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